

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Kenikir (Cosmos caudatus Kunth) as an ingredient in *Pecel* (Traditional Javanese Ethnic Salad): Potential and Bioactivity

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Abstract

Kenikir (Cosmos caudatus) is a vegetable that has long been used by local communities in Indonesia, especially those living on the island of Java. The aim of the research is to explain the benefits and bioactivity of *C. caudatus*, so that its potential can be increased. The research method was carried out using surveys, interviews and literature studies. The respondent is a *pecel* trader who uses *kenikir* as an its ingredient. Secondary data was obtained online using the keywords *C. caudatus* and bioactivity of *C. caudatus*. *Kenikir* is a perennial herb with lobed leaves with capitulum flowers. Local people in Jatisampurna use *C. caudatus* as an ingredient for *lalapan* (vegetables consumed fresh) and for *pecel* (a traditional Javanese ethnic salad). The distinctive aroma of *C. caudatus* leaves makes it suitable for consumption in fresh form or as simple preparations. In traditional medicine, *C. caudatus* is used to treat various diseases such as osteoporosis and for beauty (preventing aging). The *C. caudatus* is rich in nutrients such as protein, fiber, Vit C, Vit B1, Vit B2, Beta Carotene, Potassium, Calcium, Iron and Phosphorus. The bioactivity of *C. caudatus* 's is anti-microbial, tea herbal, anti-osteoporosis, anti-diabetes mellitus, anti-oxidant, neuroprotection, beauty, anti-hypertension and anti-cancer. The use of *C. caudatus* as a traditional salad and beauty ingredient needs to be researched further so that it becomes an alternative as a natural anti-aging agent.

Keywords: *Cosmos caudatus*; Traditional salad; Anti-aging; Tea herbal

1. Introduction

Kenikir (Cosmos caudatus Kunth) is a vegetable that has been long used by local communities in Indonesia, especially those living on the island of Java. In Southeast Asia, *C. caudatus* is also used in traditional medicine [1,2,3], culinary and therapy [4]. In Malaysia, *C. caudatus* known as ulam raja can be eaten raw with rice [5], an appetizer [6] in the form of salad [7].

Research researchers reported bioactivities of *C. caudatus* such as anti-diabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-hypertensive [1,8,9], anti-microbial [1,9], anti- bacterial, anti-fungal, anti-osteoporosis, anti-hyperlipidemia, anti-cancer, anti-hepatoprotective, and to overcome fertility problems [8] (, healthy bone formation [9]. In traditional medicine, *C. caudatus* is used in healing bone fractures in conditions of osteoporosis [1,10]. The utilization and bioactivity of *C. caudatus* is related to the content of secondary metabolites [4] such as flavonoids and essential oils.

The *C. caudatus* also has the potential to be developed as a herbal tea because it contains high levels of antioxidant compounds [5,11]. The addition of *C. caudatus* leaves to other food ingredients can improve quality, provide a healthier effect [5] and can be developed into future anti-aging products [12]. The addition of *C. caudatus* extract at a dose of 500 mg/kg to beef patties showed a strong lipid oxidation inhibitory effect [5].

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Silalahi et al [13] stated that *C. caudatus* has long been bought and sold in traditional markets in West Java, where it is used as an ingredient for *lalapan* (vegetables consumed raw) and as an ingredient for other vegetables, including the ingredients for making *pecel*. The *pecel* is a traditional Indonesian salad made from various boiled vegetables added with peanut sauce (Figure 1). Initially *pecel* was associated with Javanese ethnicity, but now it is consumed by the majority of Indonesian people. Empirically, it can be seen that the types of vegetables used as *pecel* ingredients vary from one region to another, depending on the biodiversity found in the surrounding environment. Based on a field survey we conducted, several *pecel* traders in the Jatisampurna area use *C. caudatus* as one of their main ingredients. This study aims to explain the use and bioactivity of *C. caudatus* so that its development and use as an alternative ingredient for traditional salads can be improved.

Figure 1 Processed *kenikir* (*C. caudatus*). A. Boiled *kenikir* leaves together with other vegetables are served as an ingredient for *pecel*. B. The *kenikir* as ingredient *pecel* is equipped with a topping of peanut brittle

2. Research Methods

The research method was carried out using surveys and interviews with *pecel* traders in Jatisampurna, Bekasi, West Java. Respondents are traders who use *kenikir* as a of the ingredients for making *pecel*. To complete the *kenikir* bioactivity, secondary data was used sourced from articles published online using the keywords *C. caudatus* and bioactivity of *C. caudatus*. The data and information obtained were synthesized to explain the botany, benefits, bioactivity and potential of *C. caudatus* as a traditional salad.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Botany of *Cosmos caudatus* Kunth

The Asteraceae family is one of the largest families of flowering plants, with more than 1600 genera and 25,000 species worldwide [14]. Asteraceae flowers have the characteristic that the flowers are bisexual, female and male, surrounded by small leaves, and form a capitulum [15]. *Cosmos caudatus* is a species that is widely used as food and traditional medicine.

Description *C. caudatus*: A showy flowered, tall and annual herb, lateral, herbaceous, round, glabrous with some hairy. Leaves opposite, compound bipinnate, exstipulate, petiole 3.5cm. long lobed or 2-3 pinnatisect, area covered (7.8cm. L x 7.6cm. B), attenuate, acuminate, entire, hairy, membranous, dorsiventral, reticulate and green colour. Inflorescence solitary or loosely corymbose. Hermaphrodite florets with slender arms thickened upwards, hirsute, with short, acute appendages, receptacle concev, ovary inferior, 1-ovule, basal placentation [16,17].

Figure 2 Kenikir (*C. caudatus*). A. A bunch of *C. caudatus* is sold in the market showing the morphological structure of the leaves; B. Kenikir with other types of vegetables sold in the market

3.2. Uses and bioactivity

The local people in Indonesia have long used *C. caudatus* as an ingredient for fresh vegetables, vegetables and *pecel*. To meet consumers, various traders at the Kranggan market (Jatisampurna) have been selling *C. caudatus* (Figure 2). The distinctive aroma of the leaves makes this plant delicious to consume both in fresh and processed form. In processed *pecel* (Figure 1), *C. caudatus* is boiled briefly (5 minutes). The use of *C. caudatus* as a salad ingredient is related to its nutritional content and has great potential to be developed as an alternative food ingredient. Hui et al [18] reported that every 100 g of *C. caudatus* contains protein (2.9 g), fiber (1.6 g) and is rich in Vit C, Vit B1, Vit B2, Beta Carotene, Potassium, Calcium, Iron and Phosphorus.

In traditional medicine, *C. caudatus* is used to strengthen bones, treat cardiovascular disorders [2,7], slow aging [2,3], reduce fever, treat infections, improve skin texture [7], and prevent degenerative diseases [3]. Based on the literature review that we obtained, *kenikir* has various benefits and bioactivity such as antidiabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive [1,8,9], anti-microbial [1,9], antibacterial, antifungal, anti-osteoporotic, antihyperlipidemic, anticancer, anti-hepatoprotective, and to overcome fertility problems [8], healthy bone formation, and blood glucose levels [9]. Below we will explain *C. caudatus* bioactivities as anti-microbial, herbal, anti-osteoporosis, anti-diabetes mellitus, anti-oxidant, neuroprotection, anti-hypertension and anti-cancer.

3.2.1. Anti-microbial

The bioactivity of *C. caudatus* as an anti-microbial has been reported by Yusoff et al [19], Sia et al [20], Yusoff et al [21], Yusof et al [22]. The *C. caudatus* inhibits the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* [20,22], *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [19,20], *Bacillus cereus*, *B. subtilis*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and *Candida albicans* [19], and *Salmonella* sp. [20]. Bioactive compounds thought to be related to antimicrobials are palmitic acid, stigmasterol, phytol and neophytadiene [22].

The antimicrobial bioactivity of *C. caudatus* is influenced by pH, temperature and type of microbe. The *C. caudatus* leaf ethanol extract inhibits the growth of both Gram positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram negative (*E. coli*) bacteria with an inhibition zone (22-24 mm) the same as commercial antiseptics [22]. The *C. caudatus* leaf extract increases its antimicrobial activity at lower acidity (pH 3) and higher temperature (50°C) against most pathogens [21]. The killing time curve of *C. caudatus* extract for *B. cereus*, *B. subtilis*, *P. mirabilis*, *P. aeruginosa* and *C. albicans* at concentration was directly proportional to concentration [19]. The *C. caudatus*'s ability to inhibit microbial growth has great potential for development in food cleaners [21], natural antimicrobial agents [19] and commercial antiseptics [22].

3.2.2. Herbal Tea

Consumption of herbal tea is increasing because it tastes refreshing and has a positive impact on health, is easy to obtain, has abundant resources and cheaper prices [23]. Herbal tea made from young *C. caudatus* leaves has very strong antioxidant activity compared to that made from mature and old leaves [11], but the mineral content of tea from old leaves is higher than that from mature and young leaves [23,24]. Different stages of maturity of plants used as raw materials can influence antioxidant activity, color and mineral content in herbal tea [24].

3.2.3. Anti Osteoporosis

Cosmos caudatus is traditionally a bone strengthening agent [1,4,7,25,26], a bone-protecting and bone proliferation agent [7]. The use of *C. caudatus* in strengthening bones is thought to be related to the Calcium content [10] of around 270 mg [18]. The *C. caudatus* improves bone histomorphometry in ovariectomized mice by increasing the rate of mineral apposition, osteoid volume and osteoblast surface [10].

3.2.4. Anti-diabetes mellitus

The leaves of *C. caudatus* are rich in bioactive compounds so they are prospective for development as an anti-diabetic agent [9,27], especially in type 2 diabetes patients [8,28]. Optimizing glycemic control is critical to preventing complications associated with type 2 diabetes [10]. The supplementation of *C. caudatus* improves insulin resistance and sensitivity in type 2 diabetes patients [8]. In experimental animals after 8 weeks of supplementation, *C. caudatus* significantly reduced serum insulin and HbA1C levels [27,28]. Leaf ethanol extract and *C. caudatus* solvent fraction inhibit the α -glucosidase enzyme [27].

3.2.5. Antioxidant

The use of different types of extraction solvents has a significant influence on the antioxidant properties of *C. caudatus* extracts [29]. The butanol fraction of *C. caudatus* shoots has the highest antioxidant activity compared to other fractions [2]. 100% methanol and 50% ethanol extracts of *C. caudatus* leaves showed the highest antioxidant activity [29,30]. Ethanol 50% is further recommended as the most efficient solvent for extracting antioxidant compounds from *C. caudatus* leaves [29]. The ethanol extract of *C. caudatus* contains several compounds, such as isoquercitrin, quercetin-3-O-rutinoside, avicularin, rutin, quercitrin, and vitexin, which likely contribute to the antioxidant capacity of *C. caudatus* [30].

3.2.6. Neuroprotection

The *C. caudatus* contains high levels of flavonoids and may be beneficial in neuroprotection and thus has the potential to prevent neurodegenerative diseases [31]. The *C. caudatus* supplementation (250 mg/capsule) or placebo (500 mg maltodextrin/capsule) twice daily for 12 weeks has the potential to improve global cognition, tension, total mood disturbance, and oxidative stress among older adults with mild cognitive impairment [31].

3.2.7. Cosmetics

Cosmos caudatus is traditionally claimed as an anti-aging agent in Malaysia [12], Southeast Asia and Latin America [25]. The *C. caudatus* has great potential to be developed in the cosmetics industry because it has antioxidant, anti-collagenase, anti-elastase, anti-tyrosinase activity [32]. Skin aging is associated with collagen degradation by matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), leading to loss of skin elasticity and the formation of wrinkles [12]. The leaves and shoots of *C. caudatus* can make skin younger, if consumed regularly [32]. Administration of 1000 μ g/mL *C. caudatus* water extract inhibited the activities of collagenase, elastase and tyrosinase 51.3; 63.7 and 72.7% respectively compared to control [32]. Flavonol glycosides derived from quercetin and kaempferol, and flavon C-glycosides derived from apigenin were the main compounds identified in *C. caudatus* water extract [32].

The E2 and E3 fractions of *C. caudatus* inhibited collagenase activity, MMP-1 and MMP-3 mRNA and protein expression, as well as NF- κ B activation induced by TNF- α in *C. caudatus* D-966SK cells. Most *C. caudatus* consists of flavonoids and their glycosides such as Quercitrin (14.79% w/w) and quercetin (11.20% w/w) inhibit collagenase activity [12]. The *C. caudatus* fraction rich in flavonoid glycosides showed skin anti-aging effects through inhibiting collagenase, MMP-1 and MMP-3 activities, possibly via the NF- κ B pathway. *C. caudatus* which reveals its potential to be developed as an anti-aging product in the future [12].

3.2.8. Anti Hypertension

The *C. caudatus* is a medicinal herb used traditionally in Latin America and Southeast Asia for cardiovascular uses [25]. The butanol fraction of *C. caudatus* had the highest inhibitory effect at IC₂₅ on the migration and invasion of vascular smooth muscle cells which accounted for 53.93% and 59.94%, respectively. Butanol extract and ethanol extract fractions at IC₁₀ displayed the highest invasion inhibition index (around 68%) [25].

3.2.9. Anticancer

The ethanol extract and ethyl acetate extract of *C. caudatus* leaves increase anticancer activity. The Microtetrazolium test shows that the ethanol extract and ethyl acetate extract of *C. caudatus* leaves have strong cytotoxic activity with IC₅₀ of 17.46 ppm and 6.31 ppm respectively [33]. Fractions F2, F7 and F8 *C. caudatus* showed strong dose-dependent cytotoxicity on Human Colorectal Carcinoma Cells with IC₅₀ values of 15.53 ± 0.4, 32.72 ± 0.3 and 34.16 ± 1.4 µg/mL respectively [20].

4. Conclusion

- *Kenikir* (*C. caudatus*) is a perennial herb with lobed leaves with capitulum flowers.
- Local people in the Jatisampurna, West Java use *C. caudatus* as an ingredient for fresh vegetables, vegetables and *pecel*. The distinctive aroma of the leaves makes this plant delicious to consume both in fresh and processed form.
- The *C. caudatus* has bioactivity as anti-microbial, herbal, anti-osteoporosis, anti-diabetes mellitus, anti-oxidant, nerve protection, cosmetic, anti-hypertension and anti-cancer.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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